

Evidence Academy Consensus Building Workshop

Please see below for themes that emerged out of the facilitated workshop in response to the below prompt.

Question: *Based on your experience, the action steps we can take to share and apply the community engagement strategies from RADx-UP to advance health equity research and practice are...?*

Theme (as identified by workshop participants)	Ideas/strategies within each theme (as identified by workshop participants)
Co-create tailored and responsive messaging	Audience specific toolkits (researchers, policy makers, health leaders)
	Language accessibility (language and terminology) to ensure relevant audiences
	Data visualizations & infographics for consortia outcomes
	Contextual project story-telling with a wide lens
Disseminate impacts beyond RADx-UP community	Transfer & translate knowledge to federal/political officials for application to public policy
	Federally funded PSA about health inequity research and tools
	Op Eds by researchers and PIs
Shift power to maintain equitable partnerships	Conduct intercultural communication workshop before bringing partners together
	Use decolonizing approach and address historical power imbalance
	Dismantle "savior" mentality when working with communities
	Utilize community liaison roles to assist in finding access to health services
	Include community members in every step of the process (Representation matters)
	Investing in/finding ways to boost representation in healthcare settings. Build pathways for community members to be a part of the health care being provided.
Tailor strategies to the community's needs	Use technology that is relevant to the target group: Ex: YouTube or Facebook or Radio
	Tailor strategies to specific need needs of a community - one size does not fit all
	Building foundational skills for finding healthcare, resource guide that is accessible to community (virtual and paper copy)
Support community-led implementation	Involve the community members from the beginning, in every step of the process.
	Incorporate community leaders into the outreach plan
	Community liaison implementation to ensure continuum of care for underserved groups
Fund community capacity building to lead sustainability efforts	Make training opportunities available that can encourage sustainability of resource
	Include a sustainability plan with earmarked grant funds for the sustainment.
	Find the money by reaching into new partnerships and going beyond your current circle
	Network with those outside of your immediate community. Exchange ideas and best practices
	Support community capacity building and sustainability
	Ensure that the work is sustainable and long term.
Establish & foster "Equitable and Effective Partnerships"	Build meaningful partnerships that promote trust building and reciprocity
	Connecting with the school leaders to facilitate testing
	Connecting to and engaging with state-level health redesign efforts to support community organizations, ensure community perspectives are represented and their strengths and priorities are honored
Sharing Research Results and Returning Value to the Community	Provide research results in multiple languages
	Ensure results are provided early to participants and communities
	Disseminate what worked and what didn't- publish, present, etc.
	Provide opportunities for community members to co-author publications
	When sharing results, giving credit and noting where information was obtained and who it was in partnership with
	Provide a newsletter that provides project information and highlights 1-2 organizations at a time
	Making sure results are shared back with project teams directly
	Finding ways to share results that are not just academic journals
	Collecting comments from individuals who have benefited from the project, in order to be able to share it
	Determine what generalizable community engagement strategies are
Advancing Meaningful, Sustainable Policy and Community Advocacy	Develop a post-RADx-UP Advisory Group to provide continued guidance to NIH
	Use collective voice to change EUA and companies to enable access (e.g., translation)
	Build framework for "Institutional" memory
Authentically Connecting Communities to Increase Impact	Letting CBOs know who the other groups on the RADx-UP project are and connecting CBOs with each other outside of meetings
	Create a network/ ambassador within the community to train others
	Create post-RADx-UP education hubs in local communities for information dissemination
	Have in-person convenings with CBOs and other partners
	Forming working groups among CBOs with similar projects, populations, etc. to share best practices
Designing and Implementing Culturally Congruent Studies	Have community partners on study team to help develop protocol, especially to inform recruitment
	Measure the engagement of partners
	Align technology so that it reflects cultural competence relevant to the populations brought into research studies
	Tailor best strategies to address specific populations needs
	Gather data in multiple ways outside of traditional methods (i.e. self-reporting)
	Having community partner on the board data safety monitoring boards
Respectfully Fostering Equity in Funding for Sustainability	Identify funding opportunities to maintain partnerships
	Fund the time and efforts of community partners and community scholars
	Encourage new flexible funding mechanisms that allow community partners to receive funding directly
	Increase number of pass-through organizations who can readily distribute funds to community partners
	Keep funding for currently established community groups
	Reduce the burden on the community, find ways to support them
Building Capacity to Learn and Take Action Together	Extend and embrace community partners capacity to not just do outreach and engagement, but to do research
	Co-learning from community incl Indigenous expertise/policy
	Dedicate intentional time and attention to partnerships
	Ask to understand what communities want as recognition
	Focus on bidirectional relationships between communities and other parties